

Pricing Credit Valuation Adjustment

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ABSTRACT

Credit valuation adjustment (CVA) is a fair value correction that take counterparty credit risk into account. This paper presents a new model for calculating CVA. The model allows us to incorporate correlated and potentially simultaneous defaults into valuation. As such, it can naturally capture wrong way risk. Empirically we find that credit spread is determined by both credit risk and collateralization. This finding suggests that failure to properly taking collateralization into account may result in significant mispricing of derivatives.

Key Words: credit valuation adjustment (CVA), wrong way risk, right way risk, credit risk modeling, collateralization

For years, financial market has been to mark derivative portfolios to market without taking counterparty risk into account. All cash flows are discounted using the LIBOR curve. But the real parties, in many cases, happen to be of lower credit quality than the hypothetical LIBOR party and have a chance of default.

Consequently, banks are required by International Accounting Standard to provide a fair-valuation adjustment due to counterparty risk. Although credit valuation adjustment (CVA) became mandatory in 2000, interest in CVA began to grow only after the financial crises.

CVA allows institutions to quantify counterparty risk as a single measurable P&L number, It offers an opportunity for banks to dynamically manage, price and hedge counterparty risk.

The earlier works on CVA are mainly focused on one-way CVA that assumes that only one counterparty is defaultable and the other one is default-free. A trend that has become increasingly relevant and popular has been to consider the two-way nature of counterparty credit risk.

CVA, by definition, is the difference between the risk-free portfolio value and the true portfolio value that takes into account the possibility of a counterparty's default. The risk-free portfolio value is what brokers quote or what trading systems or models normally report. The risky portfolio value, however, is a relatively less explored and less transparent area, which is the main challenge and core theme for CVA.

In this paper, we present a framework for risky valuation and CVA. Our study shows that the pricing process of a defaultable contract normally has a backward recursive nature if its payoff could be positive or negative.

In theory, default may occur at any time. Therefore, the default options are American style options that normally require a backward induction valuation.

Wrong way risk occurs when exposure to a counterparty is adversely correlated with the credit quality of that counterparty, while right way risk occurs when exposure to a counterparty is positively correlated with the credit quality of that counterparty. Wrong/right way risk, as an

additional source of risk, is rightly of concern to banks and regulators. Since this new model allows us to incorporate correlated and potentially simultaneous defaults into risky valuation, it can naturally capture wrong/right way risk.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses one-way risky valuation and one-way CVA. Section 2 elaborates two-way risky valuation and two-way CVA. Section 3 presents numerical results. The conclusions are given in Section 4.

1. One-way CVA

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space; \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra; \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure; $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration.

The default model is based on the reduced-form approach. The stopping (or default) time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined as,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Phi_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Phi_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Γ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Φ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is defined by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . Let valuation date be t . Consider a financial contract that promises to pay a $X_T > 0$ from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . The risk free value of the financial contract is given by

$$V^F(t) = E[D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (3a)$$

where

$$D(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T r(u)du\right] \quad (3b)$$

where $E\{\bullet | \mathcal{F}_t\}$ denotes the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t , $D(t, T)$ denotes the risk-free discount factor at time t for the maturity T and $r(u)$ denotes the risk-free short rate at time u ($t \leq u \leq T$).

Next, we turn to risky valuation. In a one-way credit risk case, we assume that party A is default-free and party B is defaultable.

If there has been no default before time T (i.e., $\tau > T$), the value of the contract at T is the payoff X_T . If a default happens before T (i.e., $t < \tau \leq T$), a recovery payoff is made at the default time τ as a fraction of the market value¹ given by $\varphi V(\tau)$ where φ is the default recovery rate and $V(\tau)$ is the market value at default. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of this defaultable contract is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left[\left(D(t, T)X_T 1_{\tau > T} + D(t, \tau)\varphi V(\tau) 1_{\tau \leq T}\right) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (4)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise.

The *default probability (intensity) approach* relies on the probability distribution of the default time rather than the default time itself. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

¹ Here we use the recovery of market value (RMV) assumption.

In our derivation, we use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ for very small y . The survival and the default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (5a)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (5b)$$

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For the one-period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ economy, at time $t + \Delta t$ the asset either defaults with the default probability $q(t, t + \Delta t)$ or survives with the survival probability $p(t, t + \Delta t)$. The survival payoff is equal to the market value $V(t + \Delta t)$ and the default payoff is a fraction of the market value: $\varphi(t + \Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)$. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of the asset at t is the expectation of all the payoffs discounted at the risk-free rate and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp(-r(t)\Delta t) [\hat{p}(t) + \varphi(t)\hat{q}(t)]V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \approx E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (6)$$

where $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi(t)) = r(t) + c(t)$ denotes the risky rate and $c(t) = h(t)(1 - \varphi(t))$ is called the (short) credit spread.

Similarly, we have

$$V(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (7)$$

Note that $\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 y(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, the risky value of the asset can be expressed as

$$V(t) = E \left\{ \exp \left[- \int_t^T y(u) du \right] V(T) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \quad (9)$$

In theory, a default may happen at any time, i.e., a risky contract is continuously defaultable. This Continuous Time Risky Valuation Model is accurate but sometimes complex and expensive. For simplicity, people sometimes prefer the Discrete Time Risky Valuation Model that assumes that a default may only happen at some discrete times. A natural selection is to assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates.

For a derivative contract, usually its payoff may be either an asset or a liability to each party. Thus, we further relax the assumption and suppose that X_T may be positive or negative.

In the case of $X_T > 0$, the survival value is equal to the payoff X_T and the default payoff is a fraction of the payoff φX_T . Whereas in the case of $X_T \leq 0$, the contract value is the payoff itself, because the default risk of party B is irrelevant for one-way risky valuation in this case. Therefore, we have

Proposition 1: *The one-way risky value of the single-payment contract in a discrete-time setting is given by*

$$V(t) = E[F(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (10a)$$

where

$$F(t, T) = D(t, T) [1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0} q(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T))] \quad (10b)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

Here $F(t, T)$ can be regarded as a risk-adjusted discount factor. Proposition 1 says that the one-way risky valuation of the single payoff contract has a dependence on the sign of the payoff. If the payoff is positive, the risky value is equal to the risk-free value minus the discounted potential loss. Otherwise, the risky value is equal to the risk-free value.

Proposition 1 can be easily extended from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable contract has m cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_1, \dots, X_m with

payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m . Each cash flow may be positive or negative. We have the following proposition.

Proposition 2: *The one-way risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (11a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$F(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - 1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} q(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})) \right] \quad (11b)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

The risky valuation in Proposition 2 has a backward nature. The intermediate values are vital to determine the final price. For a discrete time interval, the current risky value has a dependence on the future risky value. Only on the final payment date T_m , the value of the contract and the maximum amount of information needed to determine the risk-adjusted discount factor are revealed. The coupled valuation behavior allows us to capture wrong/right way risk properly where counterparty credit quality and market prices may be correlated. This type of problem can be best solved by working backwards in time, with the later risky value feeding into the earlier ones, so that the process builds on itself in a recursive fashion, which is referred to as *backward induction*. The most popular backward induction valuation algorithms are lattice/tree and least square Monte Carlo.

The one-way CVA, by definition, can be expressed as

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(D(t, T_i) - \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (12)$$

Proposition 2 provides a general form for pricing a one-way defaultable contract. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that all the payoffs are nonnegative, we derive the following corollary:

Corollary 1: *If all the payoffs are nonnegative, the risky value of the multiple-payments contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \bar{F}(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (13a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$\bar{F}(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - q(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi(T_{j+1}))\right] \quad (13b)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 2 by setting $(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0$, since the value of the contract at any time is also nonnegative.

The CVA in this case is given by

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[D(t, T_i) \left(1 - \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (1 - q(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})))\right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (14)$$

2. Two-way CVA

Consider a pair of random variables (Y_A, Y_B) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution.

The joint probability representations are given by

$$p_{00} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0) = p_A p_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (15a)$$

$$p_{01} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1) = p_A q_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (15b)$$

$$p_{10} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0) = q_A p_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (15c)$$

$$p_{11} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1) = q_A q_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (15d)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$, $\sigma_j^2 = p_j q_j$, $\sigma_{AB} := E[(Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)] = \rho_{AB} \sigma_A \sigma_B = \rho_{AB} \sqrt{q_A p_A q_B p_B}$ where ρ_{AB} denotes the default correlation coefficient and σ_{AB} denotes the default covariance.

Table 1. Payoffs of a two-way defaultable contract

This table displays all possible payoffs at time T . In the case of $X_T > 0$, there are a total of four possible states at time T : i) Both A and B survive with probability p_{00} . The contract value is equal to the payoff X_T . ii) A defaults but B survives with probability p_{10} . The contract value is $\bar{\varphi}_B X_T$,

where $\bar{\varphi}_B$ represents the non-default recovery rate². $\bar{\varphi}_B=0$ represents the one-way settlement rule, while $\bar{\varphi}_B=1$ represents the two-way settlement rule. iii) A survives but B defaults with probability p_{01} . The contract value is $\varphi_B X_T$, where φ_B represents the default recovery rate. iv) Both A and B default with probability p_{11} .

State		$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1$
Comments		A & B survive	A defaults, B survives	A survives, B defaults	A & B default
Probability		p_{00}	p_{10}	p_{01}	p_{11}
Payoff	$X_T > 0$	X_T	$\bar{\varphi}_B X_T$	$\varphi_B X_T$	$\varphi_{AB} X_T$
	$X_T < 0$	X_T	$\varphi_A X_T$	$\bar{\varphi}_A X_T$	$\varphi_{AB} X_T$

Suppose that a financial contract that promises to pay a X_T from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T where $T > t$. The payoff X_T may be positive or negative, i.e. the contract may be either an asset or a liability to each party. All calculations are from the perspective of party A.

Proposition 3: *The two-way risky value of the single-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = E[K(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[D(t, T)(1_{X_T \geq 0} k_B(t, T) + 1_{X_T < 0} k_A(t, T))X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (16a)$$

where

² There are two default settlement rules in the market. The *one-way payment rule* was specified by the early ISDA master agreement. The non-defaulting party is not obligated to compensate the defaulting party if the remaining market value of the instrument is positive for the defaulting party. The *two-way payment rule* is based on current ISDA documentation. The non-defaulting party will pay the full market value of the instrument to the defaulting party if the contract has positive value to the defaulting party.

$$k_B(t, T) = p_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \varphi_B(T)q_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \sigma_{AB}(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (16b)$$

$$k_A(t, T) = p_B(t, T)p_A(t, T) + \varphi_A(T)q_A(t, T)p_B(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_A(t, T)q_B(t, T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t, T)q_A(t, T) + \sigma_{AB}(t, T)(1 - \varphi_A(T) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (16c)$$

Proof: See the appendix.

Using a similar derivation as in Proposition 2, we can easily extend Proposition 3 from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable contract has m cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_i with payment dates T_i , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. Each cash flow may be positive or negative. The two-way risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by

Proposition 4: *The two-way risky value of the multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (17a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$K(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1})\left(\mathbf{1}_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} k_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \mathbf{1}_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) < 0} k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) \quad (17b)$$

where $k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})$ and $k_B(T_j, T_{j+1})$ are defined in Proposition 3.

Proof: The proof is similar to Proposition 2 by replacing $F(T_j, T_{j-1})$ with $K(T_j, T_{j-1})$.

There is a common misconception in the market. Many people believe that the cash flows of a defaultable financial contract can be priced independently and then be summed up to give the final risky price of the contract. We emphasize here that this conclusion is only true of the financial contracts whose payoffs are always positive. In the cases where the promised payoffs could be positive or negative, the valuation requires not only a backward recursive induction procedure, but also a strategic selection of different discount factors according to the market value in time. This coupled valuation process allows us to capture correlation between counterparties and market factors.

The two-way CVA of the multiple-payment contract can be expressed as

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ E[D(t, T_i)X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t] - E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \right\} \quad (18)$$

3. Implementation

We develop a practical framework for calculating two-way CVA at counterparty portfolio level based on the theory described above.

Two parties are denoted as A and B . All calculations are from the perspective of party A . Let the valuation date be t . The CVA computation procedure consists of the following steps.

One core element of the trading credit risk modeling is the Monte Carlo scenario generation (market evolution). This must be able to run a large number of scenarios for each risk factor with flexibility over parameterization of processes and treatment of correlation between underlying factors. Credit exposure may be calculated under real probability measure, while CVA or pricing counterparty credit risk should be conducted under risk-neutral probability measure.

For ease of illustration, we choose a vanilla interest rate swap, as interest rate swaps collectively account for around two-thirds of both the notional and market value of all outstanding derivatives

Assume that party A pays a fixed rate, while party B pays a floating-rate. Assume that there are M time buckets (T_0, T_1, \dots, T_M) in each scenario and N cash flows in the sample swap. Let consider scenario j first.

For swaplet i , there are four important dates: the fixing date $t_{i,f}$, the starting date $t_{i,s}$, the ending date $t_{i,e}$ and the payment date $t_{i,p}$. In general, these dates are not coincidently at the simulation time buckets. The time relationship between swaplet i and the simulation time buckets is illustrated in Figure B1.

Figure B1: An interest rate swaplet

The floating leg of the swaplet is reset at the fixing date $t_{i,f}$ with the starting date $t_{i,s}$, the ending date $t_{i,e}$, and the payment date $t_{i,p}$. The simulation time buckets are $T_j, T_{j+1}, \dots, T_{k+1}$. The simulated interest rate curve is starting at $t_{i,f}$. Both fixed rate payments and floating-rate payments occur on the same payment dates.

The cash flow of swaplet i is determined at the fixing date $t_{i,f}$ that is assumed to be between the simulation time buckets T_j and T_{j+1} . First, we need to create an interest rate curve observed at $t_{i,f}$ by interpolating the interest rate curves simulated at T_j and T_{j+1} via either Brownian Bridge or linear interpolation. The linear interpolation is the expectation of the Brownian Bridge. Then we can calculate the payoff of swaplet i at scenario j as

$$\chi_{j,i} = N(F(t_{i,f}; t_{i,s}, t_{i,e}) - R)\delta(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e}) \quad (\text{B1})$$

where N denotes the notional; $F(t_{i,f}; t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$ denotes the simply compounded forward rate reset at $t_{i,f}$ for the forward period $(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$; $\delta(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$ denotes the accrual factor or day count fraction for the period $(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$ and R denotes the fixed rate.

The cash flow amount calculated by (B1) is paid on the payment date $t_{i,p}$. This value should be allocated into *the nearest previous time bucket* T_k as:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k,i} = \chi_{j,i} D(T_k, t_{i,p}) \quad (\text{B2})$$

where $D(T_k, t_{i,p})$ denotes the risk-free discount factor based on the interest rate curve simulated at T_k .

Cash flow generation for products without early-exercise provision is quite straightforward. For early-exercise products, one can use the approach proposed by Longstaff and Schwartz (2001) to obtain the optimal exercise boundaries and then the payoffs.

For netting, we add all cash flows together at the same scenario and the same time bucket to recognize offsetting. The aggregated cash flow under netting at scenario j and time bucket k is given by

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k} = \sum_i \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,i} \quad (\text{B3})$$

For nonnetting, we divided cash flows into positive and negative groups and add them separately. In other words, the offsetting is not recognized. The aggregated cash flows under nonnetting at scenario j and time bucket k are given by

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k} = \begin{cases} \sum_l \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,l} & \text{if } \chi_{j,k,l} \geq 0 \\ \sum_m \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,m} & \text{if } \chi_{j,k,m} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{B4})$$

After aggregating all cash flows via netting, one can price a portfolio in the same manner as pricing a single deal. We assume that the reader is familiar with the least square Monte Carlo valuation model proposed by Longstaff and Schwartz (2001) and thus do not repeat some well-known procedures for brevity.

If the counterparty portfolio is collateralized, we can calculate the risky value based on equation (21) of Xiao (2013b). If there is no collateral agreement, we can price the portfolio according to Proposition 4 in this paper.

CVA is by definition the difference between the risk-free portfolio value and the true (or risky or defaultable) portfolio value.

4. Conclusion

This article presents a framework for pricing risky contracts and their CVAs. The model relies on the probability distribution of the default jump rather than the default jump itself, because the default jump is normally inaccessible. We find that the valuation of risky assets and their CVAs, in most situations, has a backward recursive nature and requires a backward induction valuation. An intuitive explanation is that two counterparties implicitly sell each other an option to default when entering into an OTC derivative transaction. If we assume that a default may occur at any time, the default options are American style options. If we assume that a default may only happen on the payment dates, the default options are Bermudan style options. Both Bermudan and American options require backward induction valuations.

Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based framework (see appendix) for calculating two-way CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong/right way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

Appendix

5. Proofs

Proof of Proposition 1: Under the one-way credit risk assumption, we only consider the default risk when the asset is in the money. Assume that a default may only occur on the payment date. Therefore, the risky value of the asset at t is the discounted expectation of all possible payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[1_{X_T \geq 0}(p(t, T) + \varphi(T)q(t, T)) + 1_{X_T < 0}\right]X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0}(1 - \varphi(T))q(t, T)\right]X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left[F(t, T)X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1a})$$

where

$$F(t, T) = D(t, T)\left[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0}q(t, T)(1 - \varphi(T))\right] \quad (\text{A1b})$$

Proof of Proposition 2: Let $t = T_0$. On the first payment day, let $V(T_1)$ denote the risky value of the asset excluding the current cash flow X_1 . According to Proposition 1, the risky value of the asset at t is given by

$$V(t) = E\left[F(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V(T_1)) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A2a})$$

where

$$F(T_0, T_1) = D(T_0, T_1)\left[1 - 1_{(V(T_1) + X_1) \geq 0}q(T_0, T_1)(1 - \varphi(T_1))\right] \quad (\text{A2b})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V(T_1) = E\left[F(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V(T_2)) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right] \quad (\text{A3})$$

Note that $F(T_0, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left[F(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V(T_1)) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] = E\left[F(T_0, T_1)X_1 \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &\quad + E\left\{F(T_0, T_1)\left[E\left(F(T_1, T_2)X_2 \middle| \mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right) + E\left(F(T_1, T_2)V(T_2) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right)\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] + E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^1 F(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)V(T_2) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A5})$$

Proof of Proposition 3: We assume that a default may only occur on the payment date. At time T , there are four possible states: 1) both A and B survive, 2) A defaults but B survives, 3) A survives but B defaults, and 4) both A and B default. The joint distributions of A and B are given by (15). Depending on whether the payoff is in the money or out of the money at T , we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{D(t,T)\left[1_{X_T \geq 0}\langle p_{00}(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)p_{01}(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_{10}(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)p_{11}(t,T) \rangle X_T \Big| \mathcal{F}_t\right.\right. \\ &\quad \left.\left.+ 1_{X_T < 0}\langle p_{00}(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_{01}(t,T) + \varphi_A(T)p_{10}(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)p_{11}(t,T) \rangle X_T \Big| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (\text{A6a}) \\ &= E\left(K(t,T)X_T \Big| \mathcal{F}_t\right) = E\left[D(t,T)\left(1_{X_T \geq 0}k_B(t,T) + 1_{X_T < 0}k_A(t,T)\right)X_T \Big| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k_B(t,T) &= p_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)q_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) \\ &\quad + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) + \sigma_{AB}(t,T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (\text{A6b}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} k_A(t,T) &= p_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \varphi_A(T)q_A(t,T)p_B(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_A(t,T)q_B(t,T) \\ &\quad + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) + \sigma_{AB}(t,T)(1 - \varphi_A(T) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (\text{A6c}) \end{aligned}$$

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